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Kadi (I) Case: Conflict of Legal Systems or Development of International Law?

Abstract:

This article explores various views of legal scholars concerning the Judgement given by the European Court of Justice in 2008 in the so-called *Kadi (I)* case. With the benefit of hindsight, this article accomplishes further analysis and evaluation of the case and its possible outcome for European and international legal systems. Focus is put on the position of the Court in those legal systems and its authority to evaluate norms originating from the United Nations.

Key words: fragmentation, universalism, sanctions, human rights, legal hierarchy

Sprawa *Kadi (I)*: konflikt prawnych systemów czy rozwój prawa międzynarodowego?

Artykuł porusza problematykę sporu w doktrynie powstałego na podstawie wyroku Europejskiego Trybunału Sprawiedliwości z 2008 r. w sprawie *Kadi (I)*. Traktując za punkt wyjścia poglądy obecne w doktrynie, autor rozwija analizę wspomnianej sprawy i dokonuje jej oceny z perspektywy czasu w kontekście skutków dla europejskiego i międzynarodowego systemu prawnego. Główny nacisk położony jest na pozycję Trybunału we wspomnianych systemach i jego kompetencji do oceny norm pochodzących z ONZ.

Słowa kluczowe: fragmentacja, uniwersalizm, sankcje, prawa człowieka, hierarchia źródeł prawa

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1. Introduction

In the European Court of Justice's (hereinafter: ECJ) jurisprudence, the court has faced a conflict of rules originating from different legislative centres many times. This phenomenon was once described by Ewa Łętowska, at the very beginning of Poland's existence within the European Union (hereinafter: EU), as a „multicentric order of law”². This indicated that while the rules come from various legislative centres, they are to be applied equally and without prejudice to any of them. However, this is not always possible and the ECJ has frequently faced the challenge of assessing rules originating from different legal orders. Some of the most prominent examples include a series of cases in which the ECJ was to assess the effect of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (hereinafter: GATT), or the World Trade Organization (hereinafter: WTO) rules³. Nevertheless, the GATT/WTO cases are different from the one in question. As the above-mentioned cases affect mainly one area of regulations (trade), the ECJ in *Kadi* seems to extend similar reasoning to other types of cases, too. The controversial nature of this case is a sign of its significance. In this paper, I will examine whether the effectiveness of United Nations Security Council (hereinafter: UNSC) resolutions under general international law for the ECJ, concerning the *Kadi* case, was allowed.

In the *Kadi* case, the Court of First Instance (hereinafter: CFI) refused to review the compatibility of resolutions in question with the EU law but checked its accordance with *jus cogens* instead. Next, the ECJ itself rejected this reasoning and instead reviewed the Council's Regulation, which implemented the UNSC resolutions. That is why the research question for this article is as follows: Was it allowed under general international law for the ECJ to review UNSC resolutions, in the case of Mr *Kadi*?

In this article, focus will be put on the stage of the case, which in literature is known as *Kadi (I)*⁴, as the later stages of the case seem to follow the course once set in 2008.

I will first present the factual and legal summary of *Kadi (I)*, followed by a range of perspectives on this case. I will then produce my own reasoned conclusion to the research question by discussing the arguments raised by scholars and show that this dispute is still important in current discourse. In my own analysis, I will discuss the present doctrine.

² E. Łętowska, *Multicentryczność współczesnego systemu prawa i jej konsekwencje*, „Państwo i Prawo” 2005, r. 60, z. 4, p. 3–10.

³ See e.g. ECJ Judgement of 12.12.1972, *International Fruit Company NV and others v Produktschap voor Groenten en Fruit*, Joined Cases 21–24/72; ECJ Judgement of 23.11.1999, *Portugal v Council*, Case C-149/96.

⁴ ECJ Judgement of 3.9.2008, *Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation v Council of the European Union and Commission of the European Communities*, C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P.

2. Case Summary

2.1. Development before the case

In 1999 the UNSC introduced the Sanctions Committee, which was responsible for enlisting individuals and legal entities related to Al-Qaeda and Usama bin Laden. Sanctions included freezing funds and other financial resources controlled directly or indirectly by the Taliban⁵. Following this resolution, the authorities of the European Union (specifically, the Council of the EU) decided that this matter falls within Common Foreign and Security Policy and adapted Common Position. Later on, in February 2000, measures taken by the Council took form of a regulation No 337/2000 on the basis of what was at that time Articles 60 and 301 of EC⁶.

In December 2000, the UNSC decided to introduce another resolution, which called on the Taliban to abide by the previous resolution (which introduced above mentioned sanctions) and expanded the previously approved measures, *inter alia*, freezing funds and flight bans. At the same time, the new resolution stated that all restrictive measures shall be imposed for the period of 12 months and shall be reviewed by the UNSC at the end of this period, with the possibility of extension⁷. This measure was subsequently implemented by the Council of the EU.

Following the attacks on the World Trade Center in New York in 2001, the Sanctions Committee decided to update the list of affected individuals with the name of Mr Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation in late 2001. Consequently, this update, in addition to UNSC Resolution 1390 (2002), was implemented by the Council in Common Position and another Council's regulation No 881/2002. The latter was contested by Mr Kadi and Al Barakaat Foundation on the basis of violation of their fundamental rights (right to be heard, right to fair trial, and property rights) and lack of competence to implement such an act.

In the following years, parallel to the case before CFI/ECJ, there were changes made to the mechanism of sanctions. These were to include the humanitarian aspect, for example, the exclusion of funds necessary to cover basic needs, rent/loans and costs of attorneys in legal proceedings⁸. The form of appeal to the Sanctions Committee by enlisted entities was also added, but this mechanism could only be utilized through diplomatic channels between a UN Member State and the Committee without direct participation of the individual in question.

⁵ UN Security Council Resolution 1267 [15.10.1999].

⁶ ECJ Judgement of 3.9.2008, *Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation v Council of the European Union and Commission of the European Communities*, C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P, para. 18.

⁷ UN Security Council Resolution 1333 [19.12.2000].

⁸ ECJ Judgement of 3.9.2008, *Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation v Council of the European Union and Commission of the European Communities*, C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P, paras. 41–45.

2.2. CFI judgment

As mentioned in the introduction, the CFI did not recognise its competence to review the regulation in question, because it would have led to the review of the UNSC resolution as well. The Court stated: „the claim that the Court of First Instance has jurisdiction to review indirectly the lawfulness of such a decision according to the standard of protection of fundamental rights as recognised by the Community legal order, cannot be justified either on the basis of international law or on the basis of Community law”⁹. However, the CFI decided that it was in position to check if the resolutions were in line with peremptory norms, which the Court understood to be higher rules of international law. In this part of the judgement, the CFI concluded that the universal protection of human rights, as covered by *jus cogens*, were not violated by the UNSC resolutions.

However, before considering the above-described issue, the CFI investigated the competence of the Council of the EU to introduce the regulation in question. The CFI stated eventually that Articles 60 EC and 301 EC should be interpreted in conjunction with Article 2 EU. Thus, they jointly created a norm that would give the Council of the EU the competence to introduce such acts as an implementation of Common and Foreign Security. It was also argued by the claimants that regardless the name of an act, it was not a regulation but rather a „bundle of individual decisions”¹⁰. Those arguments were rejected on the basis that the act had in fact a general applicability, as it prohibited all individuals to take part in economic deals with entities enlisted by the Sanctions Committee.

2.3. ECJ judgement

A different approach was taken by the Grand Chamber of the ECJ. Following the opinion of Advocate General Maduro and contrary to the stance taken by the CFI, the ECJ considered itself competent to review the validity of the regulation in question. It recalled that no other international agreement shall impede the review of the validity of any Community measure, in the light of fundamental rights. The ECJ noted that this is a „constitutional guarantee stemming from the EC Treaty as an autonomous legal system which is not to be prejudiced by an international agreement”¹¹. Thus, the ECJ reviewed the measures in question, and reached the conclusion that they did not meet the standard of protection of the fundamental rights – both for the right to be heard

⁹ ECJ Judgement of 3.9.2008, *Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation v Council of the European Union and Commission of the European Communities*, C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P, para. 86.

¹⁰ ECJ Judgement of 3.9.2008, *Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation v Council of the European Union and Commission of the European Communities*, C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P, para. 69.

¹¹ ECJ Judgement of 3.9.2008, *Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation v Council of the European Union and Commission of the European Communities*, C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P, para. 316.

and the right for respect of property. The ECJ noted that neither the contested regulation, nor the Common Position, included the procedure for communicating the reasons behind enlisting of persons on the list of the Sanctions Committee. Besides that, the regulation was lacking the effective legal remedy for affected individuals. At the end of the judgement, the Court concluded that the contested regulation must be annulled, however, the effects of it shall be maintained for a brief period until the Council finds the way to fix the infringements¹².

When it comes to the competence of the Council to introduce such a regulation and the potential classification of the regulation in question as, a bundle of individual decisions, the ECJ upheld the ruling of the CFI.

3. Scholars' arguments

In doctrine, it is easy to notice that there is no consensus when it comes to assessing if both EU courts could have evaluated the UNSC resolutions. Many scholars have expressed their stance regarding this matter, and in this section, I will summarize some of the noteworthy opinions.

3.1. Arguments against

One of those critical in their opinion was Grainne de Burca, who perceived ECJ's ruling as paradoxical¹³. She emphasized the importance of the former Article 2(5), which is now Article 3, of Treaty on the European Union (hereinafter: TEU) which obliged the Union to respect and develop international legal order, „including respect for the principles of the United Nations Charter”¹⁴. Yet, even considering this treaty obligation, the ECJ decided to proceed its evaluation. This, in De Burca's view, led to taking the approach which was common for the US courts. Before the judgements in question, the EU was seen as a polite actor on the international stage with its fidelity towards international law¹⁵. De Burca referred to many other cases, including *Bosphorus*, but noted that those were not as radical as *Kadi* when it came to describing the relation between EU law and international law¹⁶.

A poem by James Crawford, who was once in Kadi's legal team, provided one of the most peculiar sources. Even though it was published after *Kadi (II)*, it might apply to the first phase as well. The poem reads that „Mr Kadi killed article 103” of the UN

¹² ECJ Judgement of 3.9.2008, *Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation v Council of the European Union and Commission of the European Communities*, C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P, paras. 372–375.

¹³ G. De Burca, *The EU, the European Court of Justice and the International Legal Order after Kadi*, „Jean Monnet Working Paper” 2009, no. 01/09, p. 52.

¹⁴ Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union [9.5.2008] OJ C115/13, Article 3(5).

¹⁵ G. De Burca, *The EU...*, p. 14.

¹⁶ G. De Burca, *The EU...*, p. 50.

Charter, which could be interpreted as an unjustified offence towards the international legal order¹⁷.

Another scholar who was sceptical towards this judgement was Joseph Weiler. In his *Editorial* to „The European Journal of International Law” (hereinafter: EJIL), Weiler noted that the ECJ in its ruling had incorrectly approached the norms, which originated from the highest organ of the international legal order¹⁸. This is notable, because by this wording, the author points out a hierarchy within the international law, in which the UN Charter and obligations derived from it take the highest place – giving the Article 103 of the Charter the supremacy over other treaties, including TEU. Weiler emphasized his view by using quite illustrative wording: ECJ was this way „withdrawing into one’s own constitutional cocoon”¹⁹.

The citation above was so persuasive that it was used by Roman Kwiecień to support his own conclusion, that if the International Court of Justice (hereinafter: ICJ) does not exercise control over acts of the UNSC, neither should the ECJ or any other regional international court do so²⁰. In his view, this issue could only be resolved by establishing a court under UN auspices, which would grant *jus standi* to individuals and control the UN resolutions. In his opinion, the review of various sources of international law by different tribunals might not lead, as Rosalyn Higgins suggested²¹, to further development of international law, but to chaos and confusion. Those tribunals might end up with different interpretations and thus shall refrain from reviewing rules originating from different centres. He referred to Bruno Simma’s concern about universality of international law. Simma in one of his articles noted that even though EU is a self-contained regime, it does not constitute a separate or autonomous order and such judicial behaviour might lead to fragmentation²².

3.2. Arguments in favour

However, in the same article Bruno Simma also argued that there is „a kind of universality that deserved to suffer”²³. In his view, the protection of individual rights justifies the distinction between EU and international legal orders. With lack of judicial control on the UN level, there is a possibility to disregard Article 103 of the UN Charter, as it loses in a balance test compared to human rights.

¹⁷ J. Crawford, *Mr Kadi and Article 103*, <<https://www.ejiltalk.org/mr-kadi-and-article-103-by-james-crawford-a-poem/>>, [accessed: 6.11.2021].

¹⁸ J. Weiler, *Editorial*, „European Journal of International Law” 2008, vol. 19, no. 5, p. 895–896.

¹⁹ J. Weiler, *Editorial*..., p. 896.

²⁰ R. Kwiecień, *Teoria i Filozofia prawa międzynarodowego, problemy wybrane*, Warszawa 2011, p. 103.

²¹ R. Higgins, *A Babel of Judicial Voices? Ruminations from the Bench*, „The International and Comparative Law Quarterly” 2006, vol. 55, no. 4, p. 804.

²² B. Simma, *Universality of International Law from the Perspective of a Practitioner*, „European Journal of International Law” 2009, vol. 20, no. 2, p. 294.

²³ B. Simma, *Universality*..., p. 296.

Moreover, other authors – Horst G. Krenzler and Oliver Landwehr, pointed out that domestic legal systems do not opt for monism or dualism in a strict way, but tend to resolve each case separately, by assessing the validity of a measure (even originating from a different centre) in accordance with its own constitutional rule²⁴. This is what occurred in *Kadi*, and the ECJ trying to assess the position of the UN charter in EU legal order, took a constitutional approach and „dodged a clear answer”²⁵. Even though Article 3(5) of TUE obliges the EU to comply with principles of the UN, it is not clear that those principles include Article 103 of the UN Charter. The authors referred to Bruno Simma’s aforementioned concern, stating that this tension between TEU and UN Charter needed to be resolved somehow. However, they do not think that this judgement establishes a separate legal order from international law, as the ECJ did not reject the idea of rights being conferred on individuals by international law²⁶.

Other authors opting in favour of the Court’s reasoning were Advocate General – Juliane Kokott and Christoph Sobotta. They also perceived this judgement as a manifestation of constitutional role of the ECJ. In their view, a similar approach would have been taken by Member States’ constitutional courts²⁷. Thus, it was in fact justified for the ECJ to do so, as it contributes to the development of the international law and measures taken by the UNSC²⁸.

Pier Eeckhout, another author advocating in favour of the judgement, alike James Crawford – was part of Mr Kadi’s legal team. However, he does not claim that this case „killed article 103”²⁹. Eeckhout takes a similar approach to Kokott and Sobotta, seeing this judgement as a European take on *Solange (I)*. In his view, this ruling may develop international law, as it might induce pressure to establish a mechanism of protection of individuals on UN level³⁰. Thus, it indeed complies with previously mentioned Article 3(5) (ex Article 2) of the TEU, as it mentions the „development of international law” among the „the respect for the principles of the UN Charter”.

The last author that I would like to mention, Rudolph Streinz, also pointed out the constitutional role the ECJ stepped into. This constitutional duty was summarized by him in this way: „Each court should apply the law of the legal order to which it belongs”³¹. In order to comply with the rule of law, the sole task of the Court

²⁴ H.G. Krenzler, O. Landwehr, *A new legal order of international law: on the relationship between public international law and European Union Law after Kadi* [in:] *From Bilateralism to Community Interest: Essays in Honour of Bruno Simma*, ed. U. Fastenrath et al., Oxford 2011, p. 1008.

²⁵ H.G. Krenzler, O. Landwehr, *A new...*, p. 1021–1022.

²⁶ H.G. Krenzler, O. Landwehr, *A new...*, p. 1023.

²⁷ J. Kokott, C. Sobotta, *The Kadi case- constitutional core values and international law- finding the balance?*, „European Journal of International Law” 2012, vol. 23, no. 4, p. 1019.

²⁸ J. Kokott, C. Sobotta, *The Kadi...*, p. 1023.

²⁹ J. Crawford, *Mr Kadi...*

³⁰ P. Eeckhout, *Kadi and Al Barakaat: Luxembourg is not Texas- or Washington DC*, <<https://www.ejiltalk.org/kadi-and-al-barakaat-luxembourg-is-not-texas-or-washington-dc/>>, [accessed: 6.11.2021].

³¹ R. Streinz, *Does the Court of Justice keep the balance between individual and community interest in Kadi?* [in:] *From Bilateralism to Community Interest: Essays in Honour of Bruno Simma*, ed. U. Fastenrath et al., Oxford 2011, p. 1130.

was to protect the Treaties and rights stemming from them – especially when human rights are in question and this protection cannot be guaranteed on the UN level.

4. Analysis

4.1. ECJ as a constitutional court

In order to understand the argument, which was put forward by Kokkott and Sobotta³², it is crucial to study the nature of domestic constitutional courts. Those courts are established mostly by national constitutions within the states which are primary subjects of international law. For domestic law subjects, it is impossible to escape its jurisdiction (unlike in international organisations, from which a Member State may simply step out – as in can be observed in the so-called Brexit³³). With this obligatory and durable jurisdiction, domestic constitutional courts are much more legitimized to disregard international and European law for its incompatibility with internal constitutional rules (a right they had secured³⁴ and applied). That is why in this case the ECJ was stepping into the role of constitutional court of a non-existent federal state, which the EU might become. Thus, the ECJ should have considered all relevant rules and treat them as equal.

This reasoning is believed to strengthen the rule of law within the EU, as the Court reviews the Council regulation (implementing UNSC resolutions). However, not taking relevant rules into account equally is against the virtue of the rule of law, as it permits the ECJ – now Court of Justice of European Union (hereinafter: CJEU) – to disregard international law obligations, whenever it does not comply with the EU law. This time, not only in GATT/WTO cases, but in every other sphere, that might be regulated by the EU. This makes the limits of the autonomy of the European legal order blurred. As the sphere of EU regulations keeps expanding (a phenomenon which was also one of the arguments during the Brexit campaign), competencies of other international organisations might shrink. For example, the UN might no longer act freely and effectively in order to fulfil its basic functions, which is to secure peace and security.

4.2. Finding the balance

As it has been established above, the ECJ should have treated relevant rules equally, and it is necessary to find the balance between the rules applicable in this case. Those are Article 103 of the UN Charter, which can be also applied to UNSC resolutions³⁵, and the human rights in terms of the European Convention on Human Rights (hereinafter: ECHR) to which TEU refers. Even though the ECHR is not directly applicable within

³² J. Kokott, C. Sobotta, *The Kadi...*, p. 1019.

³³ Agreement on the withdrawal of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland from the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community 2019/C 384 I/01 [12.11.2019], Article 86.

³⁴ Polish Constitutional Court, Judgement of 11.5.2005, K 18/04.

³⁵ International Court of Justice, *Questions of Interpretation and Application of the 1971 Montreal Convention arising from the Aerial Incident at Lockerbie (Libyan Arab Jamahiriya v. United Kingdom)*, Judgement of 27.2.1998, ICJ Reports [1998], p. 9, para. 37.

the EU (as the Union was not and still is not a party to it), the principles of the Convention shall prevail in accordance with Article 6 of TEU³⁶. At the time of the judgement, the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union was still not a binding source and even if it was, it should be interpreted in conjunction with the aforementioned ECHR.

Many authors above argued that the protection of individuals is more important than the UN Charter provision. However, human rights are not of an absolute character and might be limited in certain circumstances, as it is allowed by said Convention³⁷. It must not be overlooked that besides the protection of human rights, the ECHR offers some gateways, which should be applied when public emergency is considered. In said case the global peacekeeping organisation applied a mechanism aiming to combat terrorism on a worldwide scale. Considering that these UNSC resolutions included sanctions which were used as one of the tools to reach the previously mentioned goal, this might qualify as „public emergency”³⁸. This interpretation would be consistent with the jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights, which has qualified terrorism as a reason to derogate some of the rights protected in the ECHR as allowed in the Article 15³⁹. What is crucial for the case in question, the above-mentioned article of the ECHR does not allow derogation of all rights protected in the Convention. It should be treated as a borderline of what is and what is not acceptable within the European system of human rights protection. Given that, the ECJ should have considered this case as an exemption, as the UNSC resolutions were issued in order to provide peace and security. Exemptions from this mechanism could be seen as hampering the common objective set by UNSC, which included members (even permanent ones) from the EU as well. Those states should have been well aware of potential conflict with human rights protection system in Europe and yet they decided not to veto the resolution. This hampering effect might not only affect the effectiveness of the sanctions in Europe but also might indicate that if the Western states disregard mechanisms that were invented by them, the rest of the world might follow and find their own regional reasons to deny the effectiveness of the sanctions.

As it has been shown above, there is an interpretation that would have allowed the ECJ to understand relevant rules in a way that does not include referring to the autonomy of the European legal order. Even though the doctrine of an autonomous legal order was not novel at that time, it has not been confronted with a clash between mechanisms of global peacekeeping UNSC resolutions and human rights. Especially that there is a gateway in ECHR which could and should have been used as an interpretation guideline in finding the balance between public security and fundamental rights.

³⁶ Consolidated Version of the Treaty on European Union [9.5.2008] OJ C115/13, Article 6.

³⁷ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (European Convention on Human Rights, as amended) (ECHR) [4.11.1950], Article 15.

³⁸ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (European Convention on Human Rights, as amended) (ECHR) [4.11.1950], Article 15.

³⁹ *Guide on article 15 of the European Convention on Human Rights*, Council of Europe/European Court of Human Rights, 2021, para 12, <https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/Guide_Art_15_ENG.pdf>, [accessed: 6.2.2022].

4.3. Further development of international law

Some of the above-mentioned authors referred to this judgement as a call for the development of international law. However, considering that the establishment of UN Ombudsperson for Sanctions⁴⁰ did not provide satisfactory protection of individuals⁴¹, it seems clear that the only adequate measure would be a judicial review of sanctions regardless of UNSC consent. This can only be achieved by establishing a judicial body that would review the UNSC resolutions, or by granting those powers to the ICJ. This would indicate that the ECJ took the *Solange* approach. However, considering ECJ's position (weaker than domestic constitutional courts) and the political character of the UNSC, the judgment could not have had that kind of impact. Instead, it chose to review the Council regulation alone and to disregard possible links between UNSC resolution and the reviewed regulation.

This was done by making the European legal order autonomous⁴². Krenzler and Landwehr argued that this judgment did not constitute a new legal order, separate from international law, as the latter might still confer rights on individuals that would enrich their freedom⁴³. However, by picking which rules are and which are not applicable within the Union, the ECJ does not contribute to the certainness of applicable law and thus – to the rule of law in international law.

However, there is a way of reasoning that would contribute to the development of international law. Unlike Roman Kwiecień suggested⁴⁴, mutual reviews of law sources originating from different legislative centres might result in new interpretations, which do not fall outside the order of international law. This means, that if the validity of the argumentation provided by the Court is not based on the establishment of a new legal order, which is separate or autonomous from international law, it still may contribute to the development of the whole system. That is why the reasoning of CFI is much more acceptable under general international law, as it sought the answer within the existing system, not outside of it. This way of review is unlikely to result in invalidating the resolutions, as the UN principles are in line with peremptory norms. It does not change the fact that if a UNSC resolution was in breach with *jus cogens*, it would be every state's obligation to disobey it – even without any judgement being given. However, in practice this consistency in jurisprudence cannot possibly occur (having several international tribunals involved), it might seem reasonable to limit the jurisdiction of regional courts by granting review powers to the ICJ. Nevertheless, even without the ICJ having these powers, the regional international courts should refrain from a direct or indirect review of UNSC resolutions.

⁴⁰ UN Security Council resolution 1904 [17.12.2009].

⁴¹ CJEU, Grand Chamber Judgement of 18.7.2013, *European Commission and Others v Yassin Abdullah Kadi*, Grand Chamber judgement Joined Cases C-584/10 P, C-593/10 P and C-595/10 P, para. 96.

⁴² ECJ Judgement of 3.9.2008, *Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation v Council of the European Union and Commission of the European Communities*, C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P, paras. 316–317.

⁴³ H.G. Krenzler, O. Landwehr, *A new...*, p. 1023.

⁴⁴ R. Kwiecień, *Teoria...*, p. 103.

5. Conclusions

Considering everything that has been mentioned in this paper, the answer to the research question must be negative. The ECJ did not have jurisdiction over UNSC resolutions, and thus it could not have reviewed (even indirectly) its effectiveness. The applied reasoning undermines the very nature of UNSC resolutions and the principles of the UN Charter, which the EU is obliged to respect.

This case is even more remarkable considering that the German Constitutional Court (hereinafter: BVerfG) referred to this judgement in the review of *Lisbon Treaty*⁴⁵. In its view, this reasoning might also be applied in declaring the EU law inapplicable in Germany under exceptional circumstances. This vague and unclear wording carries a risk of being overused by constitutional courts in order to protect national legislation in the event of a conflict with the EU law. This issue gains additional importance in modern Europe, where populist governments take control of bodies of constitutional review. This has already happened indirectly, however without a reference to *Kadi* or to BVerfG judgement. In jurisprudence of the Polish constitutional court in 2021, it ruled against the primacy of EU law⁴⁶ (including Article 1 of TEU) over national law. Polish court used a very similar argument to those previously used by ECJ in 2008 – it referred to basic constitutional arrangements, which should remain superior to EU law, even though national law in question does not hold a constitutional position in the Polish legal system. Polish court did not seek the interpretation within given system. This position, even though it has been heavily criticised⁴⁷, for some might seem convincing, since national legal systems are far more hierarchical than international law.

The above-mentioned example gives a clear view of the role of the rule of law within EU. However, this populist turn was not possible to predict in 2008. Nevertheless, that also shows why the ECJ should have sought the answer within this multicentric system, instead of outside of it.

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⁴⁵ BVerfG, Judgment of the Second Senate of 30.6.2009, 2 BvE 2/08, paras 340.

⁴⁶ Polish Constitutional Court, Judgment of 7.10.2021, K3/21.

⁴⁷ *Inter alia* S. Biernat, E. Łętowska, *Komentarz do oświadczenia sędziów Trybunału Konstytucyjnego w stanie spoczynku z 10 października 2021 r.*, <<https://monitorkonstytucyjny.eu/archiwa/20015>>, [accessed: 6.11.2021].

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